

An Overview of Electronic Services in Afghanistan from 2001 to 2021

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Documentation of the last two decades is a history of making progress and the e-services revolution in Afghanistan. New generation services style is called e-services. The qualitative research method was applied for collecting textual data from different sources. It proved that e-services were launched through many governmental and non-governmental organizations in different sectors. That pave the ways to influence and eradicate corruption, enhancing accountability and transparency in sectors of Afghanistan.

Keywords: e-banking, e-government, e-education, e-passport, e-ID, e-services of police

Every phenomenon has pros and cons. Enhancing Informational and Communication Technologies (ICTs) brought new technological illiteracy and dissatisfaction for Generation Y, or Millennials. Even though, generation Z and Alpha need a new level of services. The new generations' demands are different from the previous generations' services. Traditional services have an extensive difference from electronic services or e-services. Furthermore, evaluating and documenting the e-services' types, influence, and e-services' providers is a history of making progress in the war-torn state of Afghanistan.

It is about 9 million active users are taking benefit from the internet and e-services in Afghanistan (Kemp, 2021). Moreover, e-services have positively changed the mood of business, communication, administration, management, education, new jobs, and financial activities. However, it also opened a new field of crime that is named cybercrime or e-services crime (Kemp, 2021).

Review of Literature

Electronic services became popular in the time of internet and ICTs expansion. The information and services provided, which take place on an internet base, are called e-services. The e-services provide the services for a person not to be present on physical mood. However, every stakeholder of e-services is available every time from anywhere to provide e-services or receive e-services. Furthermore, E-Services are those electro-technological usages that facilitate the user and service provider on artificial way to serve the users, which give tangible and non-tangible service (Tuan, 2021). Academic discussion on the quality of e-services has been unable to keep up with data of the practitioner sector, as it does with many other elements of electronic services (Buckley, 2003).

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Types of e-Services

E-services are the shorter form of Electronic services. There are two types of e-services identities, one that provides e-services are called the service provider and the second who receive e-services is called client, user, or consumer. E-services are the changed form of traditional services to e-services (Lu et al., 2010; Shambour & Lu, 2011; Zaidi & Qteishat, 2012). Another author coted differently. They argued for Booking e-services such as reservation of any kind of services, Online courses through e-services, and governmental e-services is also verities of e-services (Prabakaran & Mahalakshmi, 2020).

Benefits of e-services

There are numerous e-services and it is increasing every day. Some of the popular e-services are coated here. Cost-efficient of e-services (Lu & Zhang, 2003); Efficiency and benefit for stakeholder of e-services (Axelsson et al., 2013); building relationships with organization stakeholders; having communication and access with almost with everyone; reduction of delays and problems; virtual availability of stakeholders 24X7; market availability; better taxation authentication; payment enhancing transparency; flexibility for every stakeholder; and environment friendly (Prabakaran & Mahalakshmi, 2020). Furthermore, it enhances the transparency and accountability of the organization and improves the trust in an organization (Ali, 2019a).

Research Gap

There is very little academic research in e-services in Afghanistan. Therefore, it is important to identify the strong and progressive points of the Afghan government, which plays a vital role in the rule of law, facilities, communications, flexibility services for the natural and legal identity and citizens of Afghanistan. Furthermore, it is necessary to understand e-services providers and their client, types of e-services, reduction of bad activities, and increasing and fostering of the good activities of the organization. Therefore, it is crucial to scrutinize and unveil the positive points of the Afghan government in the last two decays through e-services.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand e-services provider organizations in the last two decays in Afghanistan.

- To clarify the e-service types provided in Afghanistan.
- To show e-services influence on reduction of corruption, enhance the accountability and transparency in Afghanistan.

Research Questions

- Which organization provided e-services in the last two decades in Afghanistan?
- How many types of e-services are provided in Afghanistan?
- How do e-services influence on reduction of corruption, enhance the accountability and transparency in Afghanistan?

Method

Research Design

The data was already in textual form. Therefore, the qualitative research design application was suitable.

Data Collection

Secondary online data took as textual form. It is gathered from official documents, official organizations such as electronic newspapers, books, laws, magazines, websites, and research papers.

Data Analysis

The qualitative data were analyzed through the gathering technique in other words the thematic analysis technique. First, those sub-services of groups or chunked data were accumulated into one group which were related to one another and answered the question of the research. The qualitative data analysis procedures include emergent themes are developed from the study of exact pieces of information for the research. Similar groups' analysis or theme techniques helped us to understand the patterns and recognize the e-services information provided in the qualitative data form.

Result

Q1: Which organization provided e-services in the last two decades in Afghanistan?

There are many organizations and government official departments, which provide e-services in-side Afghanistan. There are two types of organizations governmental and non-governmental. These organizations are as below.

- Ministry of Communications and Information Technology of Afghanistan

This organization is the main connector of the e-service provider and e-service consumer or client. The major connectivity's provided through this ministry are E-passport, E-Tazkera, Asan Wazifa, and Mobile Salary Payment to the different ministries' employees (*About the Ministry | Ministry of Communications & IT, n.d.; Asan Khedmat Afghanistan, n.d.-a*).

- Finance Ministry of Afghanistan

This ministry provides financial services especially in the last two decades it starts new types of services that are called electronic financial services for civilian, business, and legal entities. Their e-services are as below.

Afghanistan's Financial Management Information System (AFMIS): Through on the government will be able to access reliable, financial information and to have control over the expenditure (*Afghanistan Financial Management Information System (AFMIS), n.d.*).

Automatic System for Customs Data (ASYCUDA): This system plays

a very important role in the context of recording all of the transactions related to the taxes received from imports. Through on the government will be able to increase transparency and decrease corruption (*ASYCUDA Automated System for Customs Data, 2019*).

The State Budget Planning System (SBPS): It is MS Excel sheets alongside the online electronic data entry forms. It is used in order to determine the usage and execution of the budget (*State Budget Planning System (SBPS), n.d.*).

Development Assistance Database (DAD): This system is going to establish the coordination between the government and donors. It will store the financial aid-related data alongside the different types of reports. These reports are shared with donors, governments, and the public (*What Is the Development Assistance Database (DAD) and How Does Itwork? - Directorate General Budget, n.d.*).

- Ministry of Interior of Afghanistan

This legal and official organization is rapidly growing, and its scope is changing from time to time. This Ministry provides below e-services to the citizens and legal entities which are as follow.

Electronic Passport: This is known as a digital passport as well. This type of passport has a microprocessor chip that has biometric information and is used to recognize the passport holder (World, n.d.).

Biometric Authentication of Passports: It is used to identify the face parts, eyes, nose, eyebrows, lips, and hand with fingers (Ali, 2019a).

National ID Card: Afghanistan has officially started making and distributing electronic identity cards (e-Tazkira) on 3 May 2018 from Kabul (Ali, 2019a).

Police Directorate of 119: To maintain the security in Afghanistan, the Ministry of Interior can take information through every citizen about the anti-national and international interest activities to the government to prevent them. Furthermore, this center is taking actions against the violation of laws, human rights, and criminals (Ali, 2019a).

Visa Extension: this service is also available on online service (Ali, 2019b).

- General Directorate Manpower and Labor Affair

This department register and human resource and provide the job license. Before they were providing the traditional job license and recording now, they offered e-services, which is faster, reasonable, tax exact identifier, human resource censes record keeping and more services (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan, n.d.-a*).

- Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and Martyrs & Disabled of Afghanistan

This ministry initiated the mobile payment system in Afghanistan in 2015. It is the easiest and fastest way for entertaining the wages and their related issues (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan, n.d.-a*).

- E-services of Banks

Among the various banks in Afghanistan, the following banks provided e-banking services.

Afghanistan International Bank (AIB): AIB provides an e-banking service. That includes monitoring e-service customer AIB accounts, transferring funds between various AIB accounts, local & international bank transfers, Cheque book requests, viewing exchange rates, reaching the nearest branch or ATM, viewing loan details, processing your payroll, and generating six moth statements (*Internet Banking, n.d.*).

Afghan United Bank: Afghan United Bank provides e-service for

customers. Such as, view of all the transactions, inquiry regarding account summary, account overview, account details, transaction history which can also be downloaded in PDF and CSV formats, transfer of funds and making payments to other account and so on (*Internet Banking*, n.d.).

Bank-e-Millie Afghan: Bank-e-Millie Afghan has some different features through which an individual could access e-statements, online banking, ATM, and SMS banking ("Bank-e-Millie Afghan," 2020).

New Kabul Bank: This Bank also provided internet-banking services for customers. Customers could do banking transactions from home and office. Using Internet Banking ID and password, customers could check their accounts and do transactions online 24x7 without any hassle from the world. Some other e-services are, checking account balances, taking a mini-statement, transferring money to accounts, making bill payments, paying airline tickets, fee payments, stop payments, knowing cheque statues, knowing branches of ATM locations, and even requesting the bank for checkbooks and so on (*New Kabul Bank | Afghanistan's Largest Commercial Bank*, n.d.).

Azizi Bank: This bank provided the following e-services features to the customers. View account balance, print account statement, view transaction history, track fund transfers, request for a checkbook, view loan accounts, pay utility bills, internal funds transfer, account transfer, domestic funds transfer, international funds transfer, bulk transactions, multi-level authorizations for financial transactions, send and receive secure emails from the bank (*Azizi Bank*, n.d.).

- Mobile companies' e-services

There are three mobile operators via Roshan, Etisalat, and AWCC. Which provides mobile money services across the country. Currently, this type of service is available in 27 provinces with 357 K customers, which makes 1.3% of the entire population. In 2008, for the first time, Roshan Company launched mobile banking. Currently, these companies' operators use e-services under different names. Roshan e-services mobile banking name is M-paisa, Etisalat Afghanistan is M-Hawala, and AWCC is My Money (Johannesson & Steendam, 2014). Some of these mobile companies provide internet also. These companies are Local Fixed Service Provider (LFSP), Wasel Telecom, AWCC, Roshan, MTN, and Etisalat (*Internet Service Providers in Afghanistan*, n.d.).

- Independent Administrative Reform and Civil Service Commission

This department provides e-services in the recruitment branch for high-level civil service on the merit base (Habibullah, 2020).

- Ministry of Higher Education

This ministry launched online academic education for the Government Universities' students due to the abnormal conditions of the pandemic (Hashemi, 2021).

- Ministry of Communication and Information Technology

This Ministry provides e-services for government organizations through making websites and other required soft features (*About the Ministry | Ministry of Communications & IT*, n.d.).

According to the above arguments, it is proved that many governmental and non-governmental organizations provide e-services inside Afghanistan. For instance, Ministry of Communications and Information Technology of Afghanistan, Finance Ministry of Afghanistan, Ministry of Interior of

Afghanistan, General Directorate Manpower and Labor Affair, Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and Martyrs & Disabled of Afghanistan, E-services of Banks, Mobile companies' e-services, Independent Administrative Reform and Civil Service Commission, Ministry of Education and Ministry of Higher Education, and Ministry of Communication and Information Technology.

QII: How many types of e-services are provided in Afghanistan?

There are many types of e-services which are provided inside Afghanistan those are as bellows.

- E-passport

Afghanistan's 2015-passport law define passport that it is an official document that is used to travel by the citizens of Afghanistan to travel abroad the country and come back to the country. Since September 2011, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Afghanistan issued two types of passports. Traditional passport and E-passports based on biometric for Afghan diplomats. Since March 2013 the Ministry of Interior Affairs of Afghanistan issued the passport for the common citizens as well (*Report Afghanistan: Tazkera, Passports, & Other ID Documents*, 2019). Moreover, for reducing the fraud and corruption and enhance the security the e-passport has 16 security codes which are used in order to prevent from fraud in the election, corruption, improve the security of Afghanistan, and prevent from issuing the passport through the bureaucrats in unofficial manner ("Afghan Passport," 2021). In addition, Afghan citizens can easily fill the form in order to apply for the e-passport from wherever, and whenever they want (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan*, n.d.-b).

- E-Tazkira

The national identity card for Afghan citizenship is named Tazkira. It is an important identification document. This document is very important for a citizen to access essential services via education, acquiring and owning property, passport, registration of a marriage, employment. According to article 9 (2) of Law on Registration of Population Records, all Afghans should have a Tazkira, but in reality, it is up to the people whether they prefer to apply for Tazkira or not. There is no limitation for applying Tazkira regarding age, place, gender, or ethnicity (*Report Afghanistan: Tazkera, Passports and Other ID Documents*, 2019).

Since March 2017, the Afghanistan Central Civil Registration Authority (ACCRA) has established an official website for issuing official documents such as Tazkira, birth certificates, and marriage registrations. Through this website, people access the different documents which are available online on the website, and the government will also collect the statistical information (*Report Afghanistan : Tazkera, Passports and Other ID Documents*, 2019).

President Ghani and his spouse were issued with the first e-Tazkira in the country. Therefore, the main goal of this type of Tazkira is to replace the different types of traditional Tazkira with e-Tazkira. To apply for e-Tazkira the person be alive inside Afghanistan. Applicants above the age of 18 must be registered with biometric data and less than two months of child Afghan citizenship could give through online services for e-Tazkira as well. Despite all, e-Tazkira has an electronic chip and contains several security details, like optically variable elements and tactile security features (*Report Afghanistan : Tazkera, Passports and Other ID Documents*, 2019).

- Visa Extension

Foreigners who work or visit Afghanistan need to have visas. In addition, those who have a plan to stay longer are compelled to extend their visas online or offline. The online method is also called

e-services. the applicant must apply online form with the fee payment slip (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan*, n.d.-a).

- Work permit for Afghans

This is compulsory upon every Afghan to acquire job license. General Directorate Manpower and Labor Affair is the e-service provider and responsible for job license via online form registration (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan*, n.d.-a).

- Mobile Salary Payment (MSP)

E-services or digitalization of government-to-citizen payments and enhancing financial inclusion, are the most important and prominent tasks for the government. These e-services are Mobile salary payments this service was first launched in 2015 by the Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and Martyrs & Disabled of Afghanistan (*Asan Khedmat Afghanistan*, n.d.-a).

- E-banking

The new era has faced many advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI). This AI has a positive relationship with e-banking system enhancement. This e-service is available for all legal and natural entities inside and outside of Afghanistan (*Electronic Banking | Britannica*, n.d.).

Currently, the majority of customers are using e-banking services such as ATM withdrawals, POS purchasing, online payments, online banking, SMS banking, mobile banking, and many more concern activities. Therefore, the majority of people prefer the e-banking system over the traditional banking system (Karimi, 2016).

- Mobile Money Service

There are three mobile operators via Roshan, Etisalat, and AWCC. Roshan e-services mobile banking name is M-paisa, Etisalat Afghanistan is M-Hawala and AWCC is My money. The M-paisa is going to provide the following services: sending money & receiving money, Airtime to-up, Merchant payment for goods and services, and salary payment. The services which are provided by M-Hawala are as follow; cash deposit, cash withdraw, money transfer/P2P, top ups, Breshna bill payment, Purchases good/service and salary payment. The My Money is going to provide the following services: Money transfer, Disbursement & repayment of microfinance loans, airtime purchases, bill payments and disbursement and receipt of salaries (*About the Ministry | Ministry of Communications & IT*, n.d.).

- Online Recruitment Exam

Independent Administrative Reform and Civil Service Commission is functioning as a core institution for recruitment of high-level civil service on the merit base. This organization provides exams on the e-service base without any human biases. That give fruitful result for transparency, efficiency, effectiveness and appropriate to social justice (Habibullah, 2020).

- Online Education

Ministry of Education and Ministry of Higher Education of Afghanistan launched e-services as online classes for students at public universities to prevent from wasting the educational time of the student (*Ministry Seeks Plans for Online Teaching Amid COVID-19 | TOLONews*, n.d.).

- Mobile and Internet Networks

There are six active telecom service providers and 44 licensed internet Service Providers in Afghanistan, including the state-owned fixed-line operator Afghan Telecom ("Internet in Afghanistan," 2021).

- Police Directorate 119

The 119 information Center of the Minister of Interior was founded in 2009 in Kabul City. The main goal of this center is to complain against misbehavior, corruption, human rights violations, criminal and terrorist activities. In 2013 the activities of the 119-information center have extended into five other major provinces such as Kandahar, Helmand, Nangarhar, Herat, and Balkh (Ali, 2019b).

- Websites

Most government administrations disseminate their information with websites worldwide (*About the Ministry | Ministry of Communications & IT*, n.d.).

According to the above arguments, it is proved that many governmental and non-governmental organizations provide e-services inside Afghanistan. for instance, e-passport, e-tazkira, visa extension, working permit for Afghans, mobile salary payment, e-banking, mobile money services, online recruitment exam, online education, mobile and internet networks, police directorate 119, and websites.

Q III: How do e-services influence on reduction of corruption, enhance the accountability and transparency in Afghanistan?

E-services ensure the reduction of bad activities and increase the good and beneficial activities some of these activities are depicted below.

- Anti-Corruption

The Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) provide the e-services through which governmental and non-governmental organizations directly connect with its' customers and clients without any third party, bureaucrats, or wasting time. This direct connection between the e-services provider and e-services receiver reduces the cost, time, corruption. On the other, side this increases the accountability and transparency among the e-services parties. Moreover, ICT strengthens the connectivity, dissemination of information, attendance, and reducing and expediting the process of documentation (Sulaiman, n.d.).

Some of the e-services are 119 police information centers, Afghanistan's Financial Management Information System, Automatic System for Customs Data, and the State Budget Planning System. through these e-services enhance the government to reduce corruption in the country (Ali, 2019b).

Afghanistan Government Electronic and Open Procurement System, public recruitment online platform (Wardak, 2019). Procurement, taxation, human resource management, open data and, service delivery (Barna, 2020). Indeed, the role of e-services and ICTs are to reduce corruption in key government process systems.

- Controlling law enforcement activities

Law enforcement authorities may misuse the laws and do illegal actions. For controlling those authorities, the e-services have a feature that is called dissemination of illegal activities on media, CCTV cameras, and complaining against official entities through online e-services (Nimruzi et al., n.d.). These facilities reduce criminal activities, increase awareness of Laws, increase accessibility to register grievances, ensure speedy and effective justice, to streamline internal administration by ensuring that there is efficiency and uniformity in recruitment, promotion, rewards, punishment, welfare activities, etc. (Shastri et al., 2009).

- Accountability and transparency

Ministry of Communication and Information Technology has modernized over 100 websites in the public sector which has helped them to make information more accessible, consistent, and reliable resulting in transparency. The Ministry of Finance of Afghanistan has initiated the Automatic System for Customs Data to enable the customs department to improve accountability and transparency in the customs department and it has expedited the custom clearing process for the traders. After the installation of this system, the collection of revenue has rapidly increased, automatically leading to a reduction in corruption and has improved tariff management (Ali, 2019b).

- E-Service delivery

Scope of e-services covers all cities and densities areas of the country. This facility ensures reliability and enhances the accountability and transparency of the citizens (Van Dijk et al., 2007; Waseeb, 2018). There are many e-services factors which has influenced of reduction of corruption, enhance the accountability and transparency in Afghanistan. These factors are anti-corruption, controlling law enforcement activities, accountability, transparency, and e-service delivery.

Discussion

According to the above arguments, it is proved that many governmental and non-governmental organizations provide e-services inside Afghanistan. All these organizations use the internet and technologies to facilitate the users. In otherward, the usage of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) expansion has a direct relation with e-services. Similarly, some authorizes proved that even educational organizations and restaurants also provide e-services (Prabakaran & Mahalakshmi, 2020).

According to the above arguments, it is proved that many governmental and non-governmental organizations provide e-services inside Afghanistan. for instance, e-passport, e-tazkira, visa extension, working permit for Afghans, mobile salary payment, e-banking, mobile money services, online recruitment exam, online education, mobile and internet networks, police directorate 119, and websites. Similarly, some authors proved that reduction of cost, increase the fretfulness, efficient usage of tools, time-saving, fast communication, and dissemination of information (Axelsson et al., 2013; Lu & Zhang, 2003; Prabakaran & Mahalakshmi, 2020).

Many e-services factors have influenced of reduction of corruption, enhanced accountability, and transparency in Afghanistan. These factors are anti-corruption, controlling law enforcement activities, accountability, transparency, and e-service delivery. Similarly, an author also proved that e-services increase the transparency, trust, and accountability among the stakeholders (Ali, 2019a). Furthermore, it helps in taxation authentication, payment enhancing transparency, and flexibility for every stakeholder (Prabakaran & Mahalakshmi, 2020).

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